

THE ROLE OF HERMENEUTIC THINKING IN IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF TRAINING FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the effectiveness of future history teachers' knowledge development based on the hermeneutic-cognitive technology, hermeneutic-cognitive technology, and the hermeneutic approach is studied. Also, the hermeneutic approach and its importance in developing the knowledge of future history teachers about the laws of the historical process are analyzed.

Key words: history, historical process, legitimacy, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology, competence, hermeneutic, cognitive, technology, trend, technological, hermeneutic approach.

Introduction. One of the challenges in training future history teachers is the lack of hermeneutic approaches, with a predominance of factual approaches. This type of approach negatively influences students' historical perceptions, leading them to understand historical truths as lofty narratives. Therefore, the issue of "realizing" history in the context of education is constantly debated in scientific and pedagogical discussions. This issue has gained significant importance in recent years in higher education. Indeed, when historical knowledge is based on an objective foundation and has a positive meaning, a nation, first and foremost, can deeply understand its historical roots. By analyzing past processes, it can draw necessary conclusions, better understand the causes and factors that have shaped real events, and, based on this, outline the optimal paths for the future, which affects the development of national historical memory.

Literature Analysis and Methods. The issues related to preparing future history teachers for professional activities, understanding historical processes, and facilitating historical dialogue have been addressed in the scientific research of J. Anderson, D. Blazar, S. A. Henry, L. N. Aleksashina, V. V. Barabanov, P. A. Baranov, L. S. Baxmutova, Y. Y. Vyazemskiy, O. Y. Strelava, M. V. Korotkova, M. T. Studenikin, N. N. Lazukova, E. M. Persanova, O. G. Davlatov, A. F. Ismailov, Q. R. Shonazarov, B. X. Khodjayev, O. Musurmonova, M. Qurono, S. Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdiqulov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriyev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, and O. Jamoldinova.

Results and Discussion. Improving the system for training future history teachers based on hermeneutic approaches is of great importance. To achieve this, it is necessary to create a new format for teaching history in continuous education, introduce new approaches to history, and avoid using ideological purposes when teaching history. The educational space presents itself as a "living system," modeling science and practice in concrete conditions. The words of D.I. Mendeleev – "Students should not only be given knowledge but also taught science" – remain relevant today. For this, there is a growing need to develop new approaches that foster logical and critical thinking, as well as creativity in approaching historical processes. Therefore, shaping hermeneutic knowledge in future history teachers means developing their ability to express opinions, not being afraid of making mistakes, and fostering the will to express ideas. This contributes to the intellectual and cultural development of students and encourages them to be active both scientifically and socially. Thus, the training system for future history teachers, based on hermeneutic approaches, will help establish active, fair, logical, humanistic, and integrative intellectual activity.

It is well-known that history is not just about past information or memories. Its great power, educational force, and the essence of mentoring lie in learning and researching the past, evaluating the present through that past, understanding people of today, and guiding them. If we approach history from this perspective, we will gain a deeper understanding of its scope and its role in human and societal development. In this regard, the development of hermeneutic knowledge in future history teachers can contribute to the formation of historical consciousness. Historical consciousness, as an important form of social consciousness, manifests as a result of the individual's cognitive process. Various definitions of historical consciousness exist: historical consciousness is the understanding that everything, including the spiritual existence of the world, has passed; historical consciousness is reflected in various sources and objects that embody past historical events, ensuring the continuity of our history and culture; historical consciousness involves evaluating the past, considering its various aspects, including its impact on society and social, demographic, professional, ethnic, and religious groups, as well as individuals. Historical consciousness is a collection of perceptions of society, its social groups, and individuals about their own past and the history of all humanity. In historical consciousness, past, present, and future are reflected harmoniously.

INTRODUCTION. One of the issues in preparing future history teachers is the lack of use of hermeneutic approaches, with the reliance on a factual approach being a primary explanation. Such an approach negatively affects students' historical perceptions, and they come to understand historical truths as narratives consisting of lofty statements. Therefore, the issue of "historicizing" history is always addressed in scientific pedagogical thought. This matter has gained significant importance in higher education in recent years. Indeed, when historical knowledge is based on impartial foundations and holds a positive content, a nation can, first and foremost, deeply understand its historical roots, analyze the processes that took place in the past, draw necessary conclusions, and gain a deeper understanding of the causes and factors that led to real events. This enables the nation to chart optimal paths for the future, influencing the development of national historical memory.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS. The issue of preparing future history teachers for their professional activity, developing their understanding of historical processes, and fostering historical dialogue is reflected in the scientific work of J. Anderson, D. Blazar, S.A. Henry, L.N. Aleksashina, V.V. Barabanov, P.A. Baranov, L.S. Bakhmutova, Y.Y. Vyazemskiy, O.Y. Strelava, M.V. Korotkova, M.T. Studenikin, N.N. Lazukova, YE.M. Persanova, O.G. Davlatov, A.F. Ismailov, Q.R. Shonazarov, B.X. Khodjayev, O. Musurmonova, M. Quronov, S. Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdiqulov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriyev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, and O. Jamoldinova.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Improving the system of preparing future history teachers based on hermeneutic approaches is of great importance. This requires the creation of new formats for teaching history in continuous education, introducing new approaches to history, and ensuring that ideological objectives are not pursued in the teaching of history. The educational space manifests itself as a "living system" that models science and practice in specific conditions. As D.I. Mendeleyev said, "It is not only necessary to impart knowledge to students but also to teach them the science itself," a statement that remains relevant today. For this purpose, future history teachers need to develop logical and critical thinking, and be allowed to approach historical processes creatively. Therefore, the need for new approaches is emerging, such as shaping hermeneutic knowledge in future history teachers, encouraging them to express opinions freely, not to fear making mistakes, and developing the will to express their thoughts. This will lead to the intellectual and cultural

development of students, prompting them to become more active in scientific and social activities. As a result, students will begin applying the knowledge and experiences they have acquired to their daily lives. Thus, the education of future history teachers based on hermeneutic approaches becomes a dynamic, truthful, logical, humane, guiding, and integrating cognitive activity.

History is not just about past information and memories. Its great power, educational strength, and mentoring essence are embodied when it not only involves studying the past but also evaluating the present, understanding the present people, and guiding them. If we look at history from this perspective, we will more deeply understand its full scope and the role of humanity and society in the development process. In this regard, the development of hermeneutic knowledge in future history teachers will allow them to shape historical consciousness. Historical consciousness is a form of social consciousness, manifested as the result of an individual's process of understanding. Various definitions of historical consciousness have been provided: it is an understanding that everything, even the spiritual being, has passed in the context of any knowledge; historical consciousness reflects past events through various sources and materials passed from generation to generation, ensuring the continuity of our history and culture; historical consciousness involves evaluating the past, considering the diversity of its social, demographic, professional, ethno-social, and ethno-confessional groups, as well as individuals. Historical consciousness is a collective understanding of society, its social groups, and individuals' perceptions of their past and the history of all humanity. In historical consciousness, the past, present, and future are interconnected.

ANALYSIS OF SOURCES. According to philosopher-scholar D. Abdullajonova, historical consciousness is the collection of ideas, views, perceptions, emotions, and moods that reflect and evaluate the past in its full diversity, specific to society, particularly to different social-demographic, socio-professional, ethno-social groups, and individuals. First, it must be emphasized that in an individual's historical consciousness, the ideas and views reflecting the past are tied to certain stages of personal development, and not all of them necessarily hold this quality at all times. Second, historical thinking must work for "reflecting the past in its diversity." Only then can the historical facts be organized into a system, and a cohesive vision of the past be formed.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, understanding the content, essence, and laws of historical processes requires knowing its history and system of concepts. Every thought, idea, and doctrine in human thought is refined and perfected

over time. Likewise, the development of hermeneutic knowledge has formed in accordance with social processes. This process gave rise to the system of concepts within the hermeneutics doctrine. Studying the significance of hermeneutics as a method of knowing the truth is one of the key factors that contribute to achieving effective results for researchers conducting studies in all fields of society.

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